

Monastery of Mega Spilaion

also known as “Monastery of the Great Cave”

By Marina Toumpouri, Centre for Medieval Arts and Rituals, University of Cyprus

Entry tags: Christian, Greece, Religious Group, Peloponnese, Classical Indo-European, Indo-European, Achaia, Language, Religious Place, Graeco-Phrygian, Orthodoxy, Greek

The Monastery of Mega Spilaion (meaning “great cave” in Greek) was formally known as the Monastery of the Dormition of the Theotokos (in Greek *Ιερά Μονή Κοιμήσεως της Θεοτόκου*). It is hewn to the west side of mount Chelmos at an altitude of 900 m over the steep Vouraikos gorge, some 11 km from the town of Kalavryta, in Peloponnese, southern Greece. The cave was known in antiquity, since the geographer Pausanias was reporting that the daughters of Proetus found refuge there during their madness. During the first Christian centuries, hermits have occupied the cave. Mega Spilaion is one of the oldest monasteries in Greece, and according to tradition it was founded in 362 by the brothers Symeon and Theodore from Thessaloniki, who discovered in a cave the icon of the Theotokos. They were guided by Euphrosyni, a young local shepherdess. The two brothers had previously lived as monks on Mount Athos and went to pilgrimage to Jerusalem and Sinai, prior to arriving to the cave and finding the icon. The icon of the Mother of God (Panagia Megalospilaiotissa, meaning “Virgin of the Great Cave” in Greek) is an important relic, since it is believed that this was the first depiction of Virgin Mary painted by Apostle and Evangelist Luke, brought with him during his mission in the Peloponnese. Furthermore, according to Byzantine historians and the imperial chrysobull issued to the Monastery of Mega Spilaion, Apostle Luke wrote his Gospel in the same cave fifteen years after the Ascension of Christ. It was suggested that Theophilus to whom the Gospel of Luke and the Acts of the Apostles are addressed may have been the governor of the region, where the Monastery is located. The history of the Monastery under Byzantine and Latin rule is quite obscure. It gained prominence from about 1354 onwards, when it served as the residence of the Orthodox Bishop of Patras, since the city was occupied by the Latins, and hence became the seat of the Latin Archbishopric. The monastic complex suffered large-scale destructions in 849 during Iconoclasm, in 1400, and 1640, when it was comprehensively rebuilt, since the fire destroyed the auxiliary buildings and important number of liturgical objects and artefacts. The katholikon (main church) of the Monastery was preserved until 1934, when it was burned. It was repaired in 1937. In 1943, the German troops pillaged it and executed 22 persons (monks, pilgrims and workers). New buildings were built after the Second World War, which nowadays comprise an eight-storey complex set in the 120 metres high facade of the cliff. The Monastery was restored between 2003 and 2013. There are four more chapels: the first is where blessed Euphrosyni, the shepherdess was praying, and the other three are dedicated to Saint Catherine, Saint Luke of Steiris and the Taxiarchs. Outside the walls of the Monastery there are three more chapels dedicated to Saint Anthony, the Holy Trinity and chapel at the cemetery dedicated to All Saints. Above the Monastery at the top of the rock, where two towers were built during the war for liberation from the Ottomans, there are two more chapels: the first is dedicated to Saint Luke and the other to the Ascension of Jesus Christ. The 17th-century katholikon is decorated with frescoes and has mosaic flooring and a bronze door with relief decoration. At the museum of the Monastery are exhibited important liturgical objects and artefacts, while an important number of relics, including those of its two founders and the shepherdess, blessed Euphrosyni, are kept in a special hall. Mega Spilaion operates as a male Monastery and officially celebrates the feast of the Dormition of Virgin Mary (15 August), the feast of the Elevation of the Holy Cross (14 September), since it holds a piece of the Cross of Jesus Christ, and finally on the 18th of October, the feast of the founders of the Monastery and of Apostle Luke the Evangelist, to whom is attributed the venerated icon of the Mother of God.

Date Range: 362 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Monastery of Mega Spilaion

Region tags: Peloponnese, Greece, Achaia

The Monastery of Mega Spilaion is located in Achaia, the Peloponnese, Greece.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Tsekouras, Th., Χωρογραφική Και Ιστορική Περιγραφή Της Ι. Μ. Μ. Σπηλαίου. Athens, 1916.
- Source 2: Oikonomos, K., Κτητορικόν ή Προσκυνητάριον Του Μ. Σπηλαίου. Athens, 1840
- Source 3: Yfantis, P., Μέγα Σπήλαιο. Ιστορία, Πνευματική Και Εθνική Μαρτυρία. Athens, 1999

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://youtu.be/6keaM1kKazI>
- Source 1 Description: Visit (video) of the Mega Spilaio Monastery
- Source 1 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20160922043332/http://www.im-ka.gr/2013-01-07-13-50-14/2013-01-07-13-50-51/22-2013-01-21-15-41-10>
- Source 1 Description: Description of the Monastery from the Metropolis of Kalavryta and Aigialeia

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Cave

Notes: The Monastery was expanded around the cave where the icon of the Virgin was found

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Other [specify]: The Monastery is hewn to the west side of mount Chelmos at an altitude of 900 m over the steep Vouraikos gorge

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: The Monastery is located some 11 km from the town of Kalavryta, in Peloponnese, southern Greece

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

Notes: The Monastery is located some 11 km from the town of Kalavryta, in Peloponnese, southern Greece

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The Monastery is located some 11 km from the town of Kalavryta, in Peloponnese, southern Greece

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

One single feature

– Other [specify]: The Monastery is hewn to the west side of mount Chelmos at an altitude of 900 m over the steep Vouraikos gorge

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

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↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– Other [specify]: Fire

Notes: The monastic complex suffered large-scale destructions in 849 during Iconoclasm, in 1400, and 1640, when it was comprehensively rebuilt, since the fire destroyed the auxiliary buildings and important number of liturgical objects and artefacts. The katholikon was preserved until 1934, when it was burned but was repaired in 1937

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Fire

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: The Monastery dates after Antiquity, since it was founded c. 362

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The Monastery is dedicated to the Mother of God

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Priests

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was founded around the cave where the icon of Virgin Mary was found

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was founded around the cave where the icon of Virgin Mary was found

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Notes: The Monastery was gradually built around the cave where the icon of the Mother of God was found. Through time there were many donations.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Notes: It was created for housing the icon of Virgin Mary, miraculously found.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

- Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

- Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

- Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

- Yes

Notes: The katholikon is the central structure of the Monastery and the focal point of the monastic life

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

- No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

- Yes

↳ Earth

- Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Gold and silver

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Pigments, binders

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The katholikon is decorated with frescoes and has mosaic flooring and a bronze door with relief decoration

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Iconostasis, icons

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The Son of God, Jesus Christ is depicted

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Angels, cherubim, seraphim

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Humans who were sanctified and the founders of the Monastery

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Animals are included in the scenes depicted that narrate events from the life of Jesus Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icons

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

– Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Icons (panel paintings) are found in every chapel of the Monastery, as well as in the small museum created for exposing the artefacts of the Monastery

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

Notes: The katholikon (main church) has mosaic flooring

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: In various areas of the Monastery there are mosaics narrating different phases of the history of the Monastery, such as the discovery of the icon.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

Notes: Inscriptions in Orthodox churches are always informative, providing information regarding the persons/scenes depicted

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions in Orthodox churches are always informative, providing information regarding the persons/scenes depicted

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Inscriptions accompany every depiction of persons or narrative scenes

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: The bronze door of the main church (katholikon) has relief decoration

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels, cherubim and seraphim

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ, Virgin Mary, Saints

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the life of Jesus Christ, Virgin Mary, Saints and the discovery of the icon of Megaspilaitissa

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: The Monastery has its own cemetery, outside its walls

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: This is though a place of prayer and meditation

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Visitors (pilgrims) come to pray and meditate before the icon of Virgin Mary

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Services and the divine liturgy take place at the katholikon and the chapels of the Monastery

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Impossible to specify

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: There are services every day. Otherwise, the Monastery celebrates the feast of the Dormition of Virgin Mary (15 August), the feast of the Elevation of the Holy Cross (14 September), since it holds a piece of the Cross of Jesus Christ, and finally on the 18th of October, the feast of the founders of the Monastery and of Apostle Luke the Evangelist, to whom is attributed the venerated icon of the Mother of God

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The rituals and services follow the Christian Orthodox rite

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The rituals and services follow the Christian Orthodox rite

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

- No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

- No

Are material offerings present:

- Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
 - No

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Offerings to the Monastery can vary from very valuable objects, land etc. to foods

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Offerings to the Monastery can vary from very valuable objects, land etc. to foods

- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Offerings to the Monastery can be anything

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

- No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

- Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance of the Monastery is obligatory for its preservation

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The monastic complex suffered large-scale destructions in 849 during Iconoclasm, in 1400, and 1640, when it was comprehensively rebuilt, since the fire destroyed the auxiliary buildings and important number of liturgical objects and artefacts. The katholikon (main church) of the Monastery was preserved until 1934, when it was burned but was repaired in 1937. New buildings were built after the Second World War, which nowadays comprise an eight-storey complex set in the 120 metres high façade of the cliff. The Monastery was restored between 2003 and 2013.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: It is preserved and restored by experts such as archaeologists, engineers, architects etc.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Apart from the monks living at the Monastery responsible for taking every day care of the Monastery, experts are working together for its preservation

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

- ↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:
– No

Are festivals present:
– No

Notes: The Monastery officially celebrates the feast of the Dormition of Virgin Mary (15 August), the feast of the Elevation of the Holy Cross (14 September), and finally on the 18th of October, the feast of the founders of the Monastery and of Apostle Luke the Evangelist, to whom is attributed the venerated icon of Virgin Megaspilaiotissa

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

- ↳ Present full time
– Yes

Notes: Mega Spilaion operates as a male Monastery

- ↳ Present part time
– No

Notes: The monks are living at the Monastery

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male monks

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The abbot (higoumen) is the leader of the community

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Metropolis of Kalavryta and Aigialeia and the corresponding Ephorate of the Ministry of Culture and Sports of the Hellenic government

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery has an important library

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: It is, however, believed that Apostle Luke wrote his Gospel in the same cave fifteen years after the Ascension of Christ. It was suggested that Theophilus to whom the Gospel of Luke and the Acts of the Apostles is addressed may have been the governor of the region where the Monastery is located

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Monastery of Mega Spilaion, Yfantis, P.. Μέγα Σπήλαιο. Ιστορία, Πνευματική Και Εθνική Μαρτυρία. Athens, 1999.

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